

7th European Congress of Pharmacology

EPHAR2016

Military Museum and Cultural Center
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www.ephar2016.org

Congress
Book

Welcome

Dear friends and colleagues,

It is a great pleasure for me to welcome you to Istanbul, Turkey for the 7th European Congress of Pharmacology in 26-30 June 2016. The Congress is hosted by the Turkish Pharmacological Society. The members of the society, the Local Organising Committee and the Scientific Committee took great care to design a programme that combines hot topics in pharmacology. All the announcements are available through the congress web page www.epharm2016.org. After the congress the website will be accessed from www.tfd.org.tr/epharm/2016 in order to make it available for long term.

Turkish Pharmacological Society, established in 1966, is a rapidly expanding community looking forward to having international scientific and social collaborations. Our 23rd national meeting, held in Ankara between 7-10 September 2015 welcomed more than 300 delegates. 2016 will be 50th anniversary of our society, and it is going to be a great pleasure for us to celebrate both events together in Istanbul.

The 7th European Congress of Pharmacology is taking place in Military Museum and Cultural Centre, located in the heart of the city. This modern congress centre with easy transportation offers convenient facilities such as meeting rooms for ongoing parallel sessions allowing you to select your favourite topics, exhibition hall for poster sessions and companies, and networking places to meet with your colleagues.

Istanbul is the biggest city in Turkey, located in the north-western part of the country, with a pleasant climate in June. Istanbul is a real must see destination with many unique features, easily accessible by hundreds of direct flights from many countries. It is the only city in the world to connect two continents-Europe and Asia. Istanbul, which has been a capital for centuries, embraces many historical and cultural beauties of Turkey including ancient and modern attractions.

On behalf of the Organising Committee, I welcome you to Istanbul for a great meeting to exchange knowledge between basic and clinical fields of pharmacology throughout the World and to share good times.

We hope EPHAR 2016 Istanbul will always be in your best memories!

Öner SÜZER
Congress Chair EPHAR 2016

P070: Hypocholesterolaemic effects of probiotics

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Due to health-promoting effects in humans, probiotic bacteria have been already used to treat or prevent a wide range of diseases. One beneficial effect that has been suggested to result from a human consumption of probiotic bacteria is a reduction in serum cholesterol levels, as confirmed by a number of in vivo and clinical studies. It is well-known that elevated blood cholesterol is a major risk factor for coronary heart diseases. Accordingly, the aim of this work was to evaluate the mechanisms of cholesterol-lowering effects of probiotics.

We have analysed original and review articles published until January 2016 in various databases, using the keywords such as probiotics, cholesterol, hypercholesterolemia, bile salt hydrolase.

A number of cholesterol lowering molecular mechanisms by different probiotic strains have been proposed. One of the most important mechanisms is through the bile salt hydrolase (enzyme BSH, EC 3.5.1.24), the enzyme responsible for bile salt deconjugation in the enterohepatic circulation and subsequent increase of bile salts excretion. The hypocholesterolemic effect has also been attributed to their ability to bind the cholesterol to the surface of probiotic cells. Cholesterol may be also removed by probiotics by incorporation into the cellular membranes during growth. Furthermore, one of the suggested mechanisms is the conversion of cholesterol to coprostanol by intestinal bacteria, which decreases the amount of cholesterol being absorbed, leading to a reduced concentration in the physiological cholesterol pool.

Numerous mechanisms for cholesterol-lowering effects of probiotics have been suggested, based mostly on in vitro evidence. Thus, future studies are required in order to confirm these assumptions and to address issues like dosage and viability of probiotic strains, industrial standardization and safety aspects.

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Keywords: probiotics, cholesterol, hypercholesterolemia, bile salt hydrolase